

Constructing models of academic funding system: relation between the amount of funding and the efficiency

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Abstract

The academic funding system has been under criticism for many years. While there are some on-going experiments trying to improve the system, there isn't any clear conclusion or guideline. On the other hand, modeling is a cost-effective way to facilitate the discussion. In this paper, we present a construction of analytical and simulation models to study the relation between the amount of funding and the efficiency of the funding system. In many of the settings, we show that there could exist some optimal amounts of funding to maximize the efficiency. The results are useful to reflect on the funding system in the real world.

Introduction

Issues in the academic funding system are attracting a lot of attention in the recent years. As an essential part of academia, the funding system is one of the major factors contributing to over-competitiveness in academia (Carson et al., 2013). Though a certain level of competitions may improve the resource allocation process, over-competitiveness may do more harm than good. Reports claim that scholars are pressured to seek out external funding, or even to change their focus of research to increase their chance of funding success (Roberts, 2007). As a result, rather than doing actual research, researchers may dedicate a large amount of effort to writing funding applications.

Several proposals were made to address this problem in the funding system. A well-known example is the introduction of a lottery for awarding funding (Fang & Casadevall, 2016). The Health Research Council of New Zealand has run an experiment on implementing a lottery system (Adam, 2019). While some people are positive about the approach, some researchers oppose such an allocation method. Most researchers who applied to a funding program with a lottery element reported that the lottery did not decrease their preparation time (Liu et al., 2020).

These experiments are useful to test different possibilities for implementing alternative funding allocation modes. However, running experiments is quite expensive and time-consuming, limiting the number of alternatives that are explored. In contrast, modeling and simulations provide a low-cost and flexible methodology for exploring alternatives. Some earlier studies have used analytical models (Gross & Bergstrom, 2019) or agent-based models (Avin, 2015; Geard & Noble, 2010) to model different aspects of the academic funding system.

We are interested in better understanding the efficiency of the funding system. In particular, our central question is how the efficiency changes with the amount of funding. To attempt to

answer this question, we develop and present several analytical models. We provide analytical results, but for more complex cases we provide results based on extensive simulations. We here construct models of the funding system, starting from the simplest case and gradually adding more realistic elements. Our results suggest that under some conditions increasing the amount of funding may decrease the efficiency by increasing the competition too much.

Although our models only capture a small portion of the possible dynamics, having a systematic construction may improve our understanding of the results. Additionally, our approach may enable us to relate our models to previous studies and study the differences. Finally, it may facilitate extending and modifying the models to study other closely related problems.

Models

We model the funding system in a utility-based framework. Scholars make their decision on whether they are going to apply for the funding, or how much time they are going to spend for the application which determines the qualities of their proposals. They receive a certain payoff based on whether their grant application will be funded or not. We will initially start from the simplest case focusing on an isolated scholar. We then gradually build up the model by adding other scholars and interaction between scholars into the model.

Isolated scholar

Suppose there is one scholar, named scholar i . Following Gross & Bergstrom (2019), we assume that scholar i has a certain quality q_i and can submit a proposal with strength s_i . The cost that it takes a scholar of quality q_i to submit a proposal with strength s_i is denoted by $c(q_i, s_i)$. The application of scholar i with a strength s_i is funded with probability $a(s_i)$. If the application is funded, he receives a payoff $y(q_i, s_i)$, the payoff depends on the proposal strength s_i since a good proposal may improve the actual research. If the application is not funded, he receives no payoff.

The payoff $y(q_i, s_i)$ can be interpreted as a combination of funds, prestige, career position, et cetera, that may result from receiving funding. The cost $c(q_i, s_i)$ can be interpreted as the time spent into preparing the application. If scholar i would not prepare a grant application he may do research instead, which could be interpreted as also providing a certain payoff to scholar i . Such opportunity costs can be considered to be part of the cost of preparing a grant application, and we assume this is included in the cost function $c(q_i, s_i)$.

The expected payoff of scholar i applying for funding is

$$a(s_i)y(q_i, s_i) - c(q_i, s_i).$$

To simplify the problem, we assume that the probability that the funding application is funded is dominated by a specific polynomial term,

$$a(s_i) = a_0 s_i^k,$$

where $a_0 > 0$ is some constant such that $a(s_i) \leq 1$ and k can be interpreted as the accuracy of the funding allocation process with respect to the proposal strength. The higher the k , the larger the difference between the success probability of high-quality scholars and that of low-quality scholars.

Similarly, for the cost of writing the grant application, we may assume that

$$c(q_i, s_i) = c_0 s_i^{l_s} q_i^{l_q},$$

where c_0 is again a normalizing constant and l_s and l_q represent how costs scale with strength and quality.

Finally, we assume that the payoff from a successful application is simply proportional to the scholar's quality q_i

$$y(q_i, s_i) = y_0 q_i,$$

where y_0 can be interpreted as an abstract representation of the amount of funding.

Under these simplifying assumptions the expected payoff of scholar i is

$$E_{single} = a_0 s_i^k y_0 q_i - c_0 s_i^{l_s} q_i^{l_q}.$$

The astute reader may observe that a_0 and y_0 are degenerate in the model. We retain them here separately to clarify the role of each variable.

To maximize the expected payoff, scholar i would prepare a proposal with a strength s_i such that

$$\frac{d(a(s_i)y(q_i, s_i) - c(q_i, s_i))}{ds_i} = 0,$$

which implies

$$s_i = \left(\frac{c_0 l_s q_i^{l_q - 1}}{a_0 y_0 k} \right)^{\frac{1}{k - l_s}}.$$

The optimal proposal strength s_i is proportional to $q_i^{\frac{l_q - 1}{k - l_s}}$. Fig. 1 (left) visualizes the optimal proposal strength as a function of scholar's quality under different sets of parameters.

We are interested in studying the efficiency of the funding system. There are various possible definitions of efficiency. Gross and Bergstrom (2019) define efficiency as the ratio of the expected gain and the expected cost. Here use an alternative definition of efficiency, since it is possible to have zero expected cost in some models and the efficiency is not well normalized when the cost expected cost is close to zero.

We propose the following definition of efficiency:

- Perfect allocation configuration: only scholars with the highest payoff apply for the funding, see Fig. 1 for an example.
- Efficiency: ratio of the expected payoff of the system and the payoff from the perfect allocation configuration.

Our definition of efficiency is meaningful only for models with more than one scholar, so we do not calculate it for the isolated scholar model. On the other hand, if we assume there is a distribution of the scholars, the efficiency can be computed, see (Lai, 2021) for the solution.

Figure 1: isolated scholar model with parameters $a_0=1$, $y_0=2$, $c_0=1$, (left) optimal proposal strength versus scholar's quality, (right) the perfect allocation configuration where only some high-quality scholars submit their proposals

Two scholars, discrete choice

In reality, scholars do not apply for funding in isolation. Rather, multiple scholars typically have to decide simultaneously to apply for funding. If more scholars apply, this typically decreases the overall chances for an individual scholar to receive funding. We now add one additional scholar to the model. Although in reality there will be more than two scholars applying for funding, limiting it to two scholars still enables us to obtain some analytical understanding. At the same time, this simple model allows us to understand how interaction between two scholars affects the efficiency of the system.

The probability of receiving funding depends on the number of applicants and their proposal strength. In the model of an isolated scholar, we derived an expression for the optimal proposal strength. However, in the two-scholar model, there are two proposal strengths involved, leading to a non-linear differential equation system which is not easy to solve. For simplicity and analytical tractability, we therefore assume that scholars choose between two options: applying for funding or not. In case they do apply for funding, we assume the cost of applying is proportional to their quality, i.e. $s_i = q_i$. This is motivated by the fact that the optimal proposal strength increases with scholar's quality in the isolated scholar model (see Fig. 1). Though the relation is not exactly linear in the isolated scholar model, $s_i = q_i$ can be viewed as an approximation to the case where the scholars follow the suggestion from the isolated scholar model. In case they do not apply for funding, we may assume that no costs are incurred. This can be achieved by a proposal strength $s_i = 0$. In short, scholars will choose between $s_i = 0$ and $s_i = q_i$. The setting reduces the system into a simple game theoretical system.

Consider a model of 2 scholars, where for each scholar $i=1, 2$

$$\begin{aligned} a(s_i) &= a_0(s_1, s_2) s_i^k, \\ y(q_i, s_i) &= y_0 q_i, \\ c(q_i, s_i) &= c_0 s_i^{l_s} q_i^{l_q}. \end{aligned}$$

Suppose there is only one grant available, for which the two scholars compete. Then if at least one scholar applies the probability to be funded is $a(s_i) = \frac{s_i^k}{s_1^k + s_2^k}$. Clearly, if only one scholar

applies, that scholar is guaranteed to be funded. The model can be expressed as a normal-form game, where scholar 1 is the row player, and scholar 2 is the column player.

The payoff matrices for scholar 1 and 2 are given by

$$\begin{array}{cc} & \begin{array}{cc} N & A \end{array} \\ \begin{array}{c} N \\ A \end{array} & \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ y_0 q_1 - c_0 q_1^l & \frac{q_1^k}{q_1^k + q_2^k} y_0 q_1 - c_0 q_1^l \end{pmatrix}, \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{cc} N & A \\ \begin{array}{c} N \\ A \end{array} & \begin{pmatrix} 0 & y_0 q_2 - c_0 q_2^l \\ 0 & \frac{q_2^k}{q_1^k + q_2^k} y_0 q_2 - c_0 q_2^l \end{pmatrix}. \end{array}$$

where $l = l_s + l_q$. A positive l can be interpreted as scholars spend their time on something to receive a payoff that is proportional to their quality, while a negative l can be interpreted as higher quality scholars less time or less effort to prepare a grant proposal.

The first row corresponds to the choice of scholar 1 to *not* apply (N), while the second row corresponds to the choice of scholar 1 to apply (A). The first column corresponds to the choice of scholar 2 to *not* apply (N), while the second column corresponds to the choice of scholar 2 to *not* apply (A).

When a scholar applies, we say he follows strategy A , while if he does not apply he follows strategy N .

Strategy N is a dominant strategy for scholar 1 if

$$y_0 q_1 \leq c_0 q_1^l,$$

while strategy A is a dominant strategy for scholar 1 if

$$\frac{q_1^k}{q_1^k + q_2^k} y_0 \geq c_0 q_1^{l-1}.$$

Similarly, strategy N is a dominant strategy for scholar 2 if

$$y_0 q_2 \leq c_0 q_2^l,$$

while strategy A is a dominant strategy for scholar 2 if

$$\frac{q_2^k}{q_1^k + q_2^k} y_0 \geq c_0 q_2^{l-1}.$$

If no strategy is dominant, the system is characterized by a mixed Nash equilibrium with 0 payoff.

At every Nash equilibrium, whether it is a pure or mixed equilibrium, we can compute a payoff $E_{2-scholar}$. If at least one scholar applies, we can define the expected payoff from the perfect funding allocation configuration as

$$E_{perfect\ 2-scholar} = \max(y_0 q_1 - c_0 q_1^l, y_0 q_2 - c_0 q_2^l),$$

where only the scholar with the highest payoff applies for the funding.

We then define the efficiency as

$$\epsilon_{2-scholar} = \frac{E_{2-scholar}}{E_{perfect\ 2-scholar}}.$$

If the dominant strategy for both scholars is to not apply, we define the efficiency to be 0.

n scholars, discrete choice, unlimited number of grant per scholar

To extend the two-scholars model to a n scholar model, suppose there are n scholar and m grants available. We here allow scholar i to receive all m grants to produce a simple model to compare with the two-scholars model. Similar to the previous section, we assume that scholar i can only choose between $s_i=0$ or $s_i=q_i$. Let Q_A be the set of all qualities of scholars who choose to apply, i.e., $Q_A = \{i \mid s_i = q_i\}$. We have

$$\begin{aligned} a(s_i) &= 0 \text{ or } \frac{m s_i^k}{\sum_{j \in Q_A} (s_j^k)}, \\ y(q_i, s_i) &= y_0 q_i, \\ c(q_i, s_i) &= 0 \text{ or } c_0 q_i^l, \end{aligned}$$

note that $a(s_i)$ here can be interpreted as the expected number of grants received, rather than the probability of receiving a grant.

Unfortunately, analytical results are difficult to obtain for this model, and we therefore rely on the polynomial weight algorithm (Roughgarden, 2010) to try to find equilibria. Though learning algorithms may not be able to find the Nash equilibrium (Daskalakis et al., 2010), the equilibrium found by the algorithm may still be realistic if we relate the models with the real world.

After simulating the strategy choices and payoffs of individual scholars, the expected total payoff $E_{n-scholar, unlimited\ grant}$ can be obtained by adding payoffs from all scholars and then take an average over a few steps. As before, the perfect allocation configuration is that only

scholars with the highest quality q_h apply for the funding while others do not. The perfect allocation payoff is then

$$E_{\text{perfect } n\text{-scholar, unlimited grant}} = m y_0 q_h - c_0 q_h^l.$$

We again define efficiency as the ratio between the actual expected total payoff and the perfect allocation payoff, which we take to be zero if no scholars apply at all.

n scholars, discrete choice, one grant per scholar

In the previous model, we allow scholars to accumulate an unlimited number of grants. Although this model has a relatively straightforward definition of the probability to be funded (which is actually an expectation), most funding schemes only allocate a single grant to a scholar. We assume there are m grants available, where $m \leq n$, and each scholar can only get one grant at most. We again assume a discrete choice, and scholar i can choose $s_i = 0$ or $s_i = q_i$. We then obtain

$$\begin{aligned} a(s_i) &= 0 \text{ or } A(q_j \in Q_A, k), \\ y(q_i, s_i) &= y_0 q_i, \\ c(q_i, s_i) &= 0 \text{ or } c_0 q_i^l, \end{aligned}$$

where Q_A is the set of all qualities of scholars who choose to apply as before.

We again need to solve the mixed strategies of this model computationally. Since the success probability $A(q_j \in Q_A, k)$ of the one grant per scholar model is related to the weighted random sampling with a reservoir problem (Efrimidis & Spirakis, 2006), it is not efficient to compute the probability and the payoffs. Therefore, we use the partial information model (Roughgarden, 2010) to simulate the efficiency in a more agent-based modeling flavour.

The expected total payoff $E_{n\text{-scholar, 1 grant}}$ is computed by averaging the sum of individual payoffs for a few time steps. Let Q_h be the set of m highest scholars' qualities. The perfect allocation payoff is then

$$E_{\text{perfect } n\text{-scholar, 1 grant}} = \sum_{q_j \in Q_h} (y_0 q_j - c_0 q_j^l).$$

We again define efficiency as the ratio of the two.

Results

We have constructed three models:

- a two-scholar model,
- a n -scholar unlimited grant, and
- a n -scholar one grant per scholar model.

We now analyse how the efficiency in these three different models depend on the total amount of funding. The total amount of funding is represented by the variable $m y_0$ ($m=1$ for the two-scholar model), and the efficiency is defined as the ratio of the expected total payoff and the payoff from the perfect allocation configuration. For each model, we present results for some specific sets of parameters. If we have any analytical results, we will simply present those. Alternatively, if we are unable to obtain analytical results we will present numerical approximations from simulations. In that case, we always perform 10 runs of the simulations and present averages and deviations thereof.

Efficiency in the two-scholars model

There are 6 free variables in the two-scholars model. Without loss of generality, we assume that $q_2 > q_1$. We choose $q_1 = 0.3$, $q_2 = 0.7$, and $c_0 = 1$. We set $k = 1$, so that the probability of being funded is proportional to a scholar's quality. We set $l = 1$, so that the cost of applying is proportional to a scholar's quality.

Since the payoffs received by scholar 1 and 2, if both of them apply for the funding, are closely related to their dominant strategies A , we plot Fig. 2 to show how those payoffs vary with the amount of funding y_0 , if the payoff is greater than 0, then always applying is a dominant strategy for the scholar.

Figure 2: The payoffs scholar 1 and 2 receive as a function of the amount of funding y_0 , assuming that both scholar 1 and 2 apply for the funding.

Multiple Nash equilibria may exist in a 2-player game, where they may have different efficiencies. We use the two equilibria with the highest and lowest efficiency to bound the efficiency in this model. Fig. 3 plots the efficiency of those equilibria as a function of the amount of funding y_0 . It is interesting to note that we can discern three distinct phases something that does not exist in the single scholar model with a distribution (Lai, 2021). The first phase corresponds to a “no dominant strategy” region, where mixed Nash equilibrium with 0 payoff is allowed. Increasing the funding y_0 we transition towards the second phase, where the dominant strategy for scholar 2 is to always apply for funding, which forces scholar 1 to not apply for funding (because $q_2 > q_1$). This produce a 100% efficient configuration. As the amount of funding further increases, we transition towards the third phase, where applying for funding also becomes a dominant strategy for scholar 2, leading to a sudden drop in efficiency.

Figure 3: Maximum and minimum efficiency in the two-scholars model as a function of the amount of funding y_0

The middle phase, which is most efficient, can be enlarged by increasing k or by decreasing l . Increasing k means that the higher quality scholar is more likely to receive funding if both scholars apply. We can interpret this as the accuracy of peer review, in the sense that peer review would be expected to be able to identify the higher quality scholar. In that case, the lower quality scholar requires an even larger funding amount y_0 in order to also apply (thereby entering the third phase), because the probability he is funded is lower with higher k . Increasing k therefore shifts the threshold between the second and third phase to higher funding amounts y_0 . On the other hand, the higher quality scholar has a higher probability to get funded, so a smaller y_0 is needed to reach the dominant strategy A , thus the threshold between the first and second phase shifts to lower funding amount y_0 .

Decreasing l means that the cost of applying becomes relatively lower for higher quality. In this case, the lower quality scholar requires an even larger funding amount y_0 in order to also apply (thereby entering the third phase), because the relative cost of applying is higher with lower l . Increasing l therefore shifts the threshold between the second and third phase to higher funding amounts y_0 .

The two-scholar model shows that increasing the funding beyond a certain threshold has a counter-intuitive effect of decreasing the funding efficiency. This is because increasing funding leads the lower quality scholar to also apply, which incurs a cost, but does not entail additional benefits.

Efficiency in the n scholar unlimited grant model

Without considering the distribution of scholars' quality, there are 6 free parameters. Following the previous sections, we set $k=1$, $c_0=1$, and $l=1$.

We use a non-random, fixed-interval uniform distribution $q_{min} \leq q_i \leq q_{max}$ for some exploration work, the quality of scholar i is always $q_{min} + \frac{i-1}{q_{max} - q_{min}}$. Subsequently, we use a beta

distribution to be more flexible while being compatible with the analytical solution in (Lai, 2021). We use the notation $q_i \sim \text{Beta}(\alpha, \beta)$ to indicate that q_i follows a beta distribution.

We first attempt to reproduce the three phases that we observed in the two-scholar model. We set the number of scholars in the model to $n=2, 6, 20, 50$ and the number of grants to $m=1$. We also assume that the scholars' qualities follow a fixed-interval uniform distribution with a minimum of 0.3 and maximum of 0.7, making the $n=2$ case identical to the two-scholar model. We simulate the model and compute the efficiency. Fig. 4 shows that this model indeed reproduces a similar pattern as the two-scholar model. While the patterns are similar, we can see that the exact Nash equilibria are not reached in the simulations so that the patterns are not exactly the same. The efficiency decreases when we increase the scholars since the competition is higher and the total available resource remains unchanged.

Figure 4: The efficiency of the n scholar unlimited grant model as a function of the amount of funding y_0 , with $n=2, 6, 20, 50$, scholars' qualities follow uniform distribution

We now explore the model further with $n=100$ scholars, with beta distributed qualities. Fig. 5 shows the plot of the efficiency as a function of y_0 for $q_i \sim \text{Beta}(2, 2)$. The results show that having a higher k (more accurate assessment of scholars quality) is clearly beneficial, while having a negative l does not necessarily improve the efficiency. The results also depend on the distribution of scholars' qualities. Fig. 6 shows results with $q_i \sim \text{Beta}(10, 2)$, which means the qualities of scholars are in general higher. Interestingly, the efficiency is not higher than when using $q_i \sim \text{Beta}(2, 2)$. This suggests that having more high-quality scholars does not necessarily imply a higher efficiency since the competition is also tougher.

In every simulation, there is a steep increase in efficiency when y_0 is small. It is because better scholars are easier to have higher payoffs when choosing to apply and they are more likely to apply, thus discouraging lower-quality scholars to apply. For some parameter settings, there is a peak in the efficiency curve, similar to the three phases we observed in the two-scholars model, but this does not happen for all parameter settings.

Figure 5: The efficiency of the $n=100$ scholar unlimited grant model as a function of the amount of funding y_0 , scholars' qualities follow the beta distribution with $\alpha=2$ and $\beta=2$

Figure 6: The efficiency of the $n=100$ scholar unlimited grant model as a function of the amount of funding y_0 , scholars' qualities follow the beta distribution with $\alpha=10$ and $\beta=2$

Efficiency in the n scholar one grant per scholar model

Similar to the unlimited grant model, excluding the parameters about the quality distribution, there are 6 free parameters. We take $k=1$, $c_0=1$, $l=1$ as the starting case. Fig. 7 shows the efficiency curve with $n=2, 6, 20, 50$ and $m=1$. We can observe the 3-phase feature for $n=2$, while for larger n ($n=20$, $n=50$) the peak disappears. While it is possible that this is the nature of the model, insufficient steps in the simulations may also cause this observation since the algorithm here needs more time steps to converge to equilibria comparing to the algorithm used in the unlimited grant model. Due to the limitation of computational power, we leave this for future studies.

Figure 7: The efficiency of the $n=2, 6, 20, 50$ scholar one grant per scholar model as a function of the amount of funding y_0 , scholars' qualities follow uniform distribution.

To investigate how different parameter settings in the model affect the efficiency, we run simulations with $n=100$ scholars and beta distributed scholars' qualities. Unlike the unlimited grant model, the number of funding m is a meaningful variable in this model which is not degenerate with y_0 . However, in our exploratory simulations, we don't observe any effects of increasing m besides having a higher overall efficiency, which is similar to the effect of increasing y_0 . We therefore fix $m=20$ such that at most 20 scholars receive funding. Fig. 8 shows the efficiency curves with $l = 1$ or -1 , $k = 1$ or 4 , $\alpha=2$ and $\beta=2$. Fig. 9 shows a similar result but with $\alpha=10$. Despite the rapid increase in the efficiency when y_0 is small, there is no 3-phase we observed in some of the earlier plots. We again observe that increasing k seems to increase the efficiency while the effect of varying l is less clear. In contrast to the

result in the unlimited grant model, where $\alpha=2$ simulations are having a much higher efficiencies than that in the unlimited grant model, the efficiencies for $\alpha=2$ and $\alpha=10$ are closer in this model.

Figure 8: The efficiency of the $n=100$ scholar one grant per scholar model as a function of the amount of funding y_0 , scholars' qualities follow the beta distribution with $\alpha=2$ and $\beta=2$

Figure 9: The efficiency of the $n=100$ scholar one grant per scholar model as a function of the amount of funding y_0 , scholars' qualities follow the beta distribution with $\alpha=10$ and $\beta=2$

Discussion

We presented three different simple model of funding in science. Although are models are highly stylized, the results may still provide some insight. We here summarize our understanding of the results, and we discuss future research questions and improvements to the models.

Regardless of the model, if the amount of funding is very large, the efficiency almost always approaches 1. This is easy to see because the costs remain fixed, becoming negligible in the limit of large amounts of funding. On the other hand, in many of the scenarios, we are able to identify three distinct phases, that showed distinct dynamics. The first phase is characterised by both low and high quality scholars not having a dominant strategy. When increasing the funding, this transition towards the second phase, where only high quality scholars apply for a grant, leading to a highly efficient funding system. Increasing the funding further, transitions the system towards a third phase, where lower quality scholars again also start to apply for a grant, thereby decreasing the efficiency of the funding system. In scenarios where we cannot discern these three phases, we still observe a steep initial rise in efficiency when increasing funding, which levels off for further increases in funding. This suggest that increasing the amount of funding in the system may yield only modest increases in efficiency.

In all settings considered in this study, having a larger accuracy of peer review seems to help to increase efficiency. That is, if peer review is better able to identify high quality scholars, this increases efficiency. In contrast, how the cost of applying scales with a scholar's quality, seems to have less clear consequences for efficiency. Our results suggest that it would be beneficial to improve the review process of funding application, while (re)-designing the application procedure to modify the cost is less relevant. Of course, the accuracy of peer review may be something that is inherently limited.

In our results, we find that some high-quality scholars are needed in order to achieve an efficient funding system. However, too many high-quality scholars may create unnecessary competition and may reduce the efficiency. Moreover, the quality of a scholar cannot simply be modeled as a single dimensional variable. Quality may be multi-faceted with dimensions such as creativity, novelty, or rigour. A more realistic model may also include such alternative dimensions of quality.

The funding allocation itself also affects efficiency. When allowing researchers to accumulate unlimited grants, we see that the efficiency is substantially lower than in grant models in which each scholar can receive only a single grant. In reality, the number of grants that a scholar can apply is limited. Having a clever design of the number and the size of grants available to different scholars can help improving the efficiency.

There are several limitations to our models. Firstly, the cost can depend on the amount of funding. It is natural that scholars spend more effort on preparing for a larger grant than for a smaller one. Although we capture this behaviour in the isolated scholar model, we ignore later to simplify the models. Secondly, the payoff of receiving funding does not necessarily translate immediately to the amount of funding that is received. The interpretation of y_0 as the funding amount can therefore be discussed. Thirdly, it may be argued that the total amount of funding is simply a given, and that it cannot be changed. However, it is possible that the amount of funding for one funding scheme is increased, while other types of funding are decreased. Despite some unrealistic factors, we think our observations highlight what might be possible when we change the amount of available funding.

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